
THE END AND CONSEQUENCES OF THE PELOPONNESIAN WARS

Urunov Shokhijakhon

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

urunovshoxijahon@gmail.com

Abstract: This article discusses the end and results of the Peloponnesian War, one of the largest wars in the history of Greece. There are also facts about the changes that took place in Athens and Sparta after the war and how they affected the population.

Key words: Athens, Sparta, Greece, population, Peloponnese, Archidamus.

The main result of the Peloponnesian War is the complete and total defeat of Athens after a long struggle with Sparta for hegemony in Greece. What caused the defeat of the Athenians? First of all, the maritime state of Athens did not stand the test of time: the policies of Athens caused resentment among its allies. The allies benefited when Athens was powerful, but as the leader's strength and will began to weaken, the alliance fell apart. Another reason for the defeat of Athens was the inadequacy of their war plan: a continental state like Sparta could not be overthrown by a naval battle. It was definitely a mistake to allow them to plunder their country. Even a highly developed city like Athens cannot exist without a lively connection with agricultural areas. Because the Athenians had superiority at sea, their city could survive at the expense of foreign relations, but with the loss of this superiority, Athens was doomed to starve. In addition, the Athenians lost a firm rule and there were irregularities in the implementation of operations. An example of this is the organized expedition to Sicily. He failed. Finally, the financial support of the Persians to the Spartans contributed to the defeat of Athens. This support allowed the Spartans to build a powerful private fleet and defeat them where the Athenians were strongest - at sea. So what did the Spartan victory bring to the Greek polis? Sparta waged war under the slogan of saving the freedom of the Hellenes from the tyranny of the Athenians. However, by supporting and siding with Sparta, the Greeks did not achieve anything important.

The hegemony of Athens was replaced by that of Sparta. It was 100 times more difficult for the "freed" than the Athenians because of their strict control by force of arms alone. Sparta's victory was slowly bringing the aristocracy to their side. A typical situation for this attitude was in Athens. The return of exiles intensified anti-democratic activities. The oligarchs supporting Lysander were putting pressure on the People's Assembly to cancel the existing constitution and return to the ideal "father system". A commission of 30 people was created to implement the reforms. It

included the sophist Critius and Phramenes. Officially, the richest "three thousand" had political rights, but the managers did not count with anyone, they turned into real tyrants. Relying on the Spartan garrison, they crushed the Athenians. Repression fell on all the democrats, respectable citizens and rich people who could find enemies in the "Thirty" state. Meanwhile, the exiled democrats from Boeotia invaded Attica under the leadership of Phrasibulus. They stopped for a while in Philae fortress and then went to Athens. In the decisive battle near Munich (one of the districts of Piraeus), the democrats crushed the oligarchs who came against them.

Critius was killed in battle, and power in Athens passed from the "Thirty" commission to the government of the new oligarchs, who appointed the "Three Thousand". However, the power of the new government was spread only in Athens, and in Piraeus the democrats were firmly established. Lysander wanted to come to the aid of the oligarchs, but Lysander was stopped by the Spartan government, fearing that his reputation would rise, and through them a reconciliation between the party of the Piraeus democrats and the party of the city oligarchs took place in Athens. Democracy was restored (autumn of 403 BC), but it was only a shadow of the great democracy that reigned in Athens before the war. In general, the essence of the Peloponnesian war was negative for the Greeks.

The new peace and the new system of government were not as strong as before, and soon the Hellenes found themselves in the midst of new internal disputes and disagreements. The war caused the origin of disagreements between civil communities. He strained the relations between the poor and the rich, the urban demos and the agricultural aristocrats, the democrats and the oligarchs. The war did not increase the involvement of citizens in the army, but, on the contrary, increased the role of mercenary armies and their commanders. The war also led to the destruction of the spirit of the traditional polis: the corrupt policies of the warring parties, the clash of greedy interests of political groups and figures - all proved that the adopted laws were relative. The Peloponnesian War was not only a strong impetus for the processes that led to the crisis of the polis system in the next century, but it was also its first stage.

References:

1. Кузишина В.И. История древней Греции. – М.:Высшая школа,2005. – ст,211.
2. Фукидид. История (ПОД РЕДАКЦИЕЙ Э.Д.ФРОЛОВА). - Санкт-петербург: Наука, 1999. – ст.349
3. Война Афин со Спартой. Fraktal-vortex.narod.ru sayti
4. Хронология войн – Пелопоннесские войны. Skazania.ru sayti.